

Immersive Traditional Places: An Investigation of Connection to Land, Lifeways and Language in 360-Degrees

Theo Shaheen-McConnell

Altitude Heritage and Resource Protection Canada, Whitehorse, Canada. theo@ahrpc.ca

Georgios Artopoulos

STARC – The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus. g.artopoulos@cyi.ac.cy

Abstract:

The evolution of methods for the documentation, interpretation and dissemination of heritage and cultural information is constant as emerging digital technologies are becoming more accessible and available as common tools in society. This research claims that digital tools that are developed to communicate the diversity of human experience, cultural landscapes and community beliefs must be guided by the respective knowledge holders. To address this aim, the paper presents prototype Virtual Tours of two areas with traditional place names by means of 360-degree imagery for Carcross / Tagish First Nation. The method presented was analyzed for the appropriate knowledge representation and access of cultural heritage information. Findings are presented to show that the proposed method highly benefits the communities engaged. The paper concludes with results pointing to the educational opportunities the proposed method offers indigenous youth. Opportunities for future application of the tools utilized for this research are proposed and indicate a contemporary preference for future research and experimentation with emerging technology to guide their widespread adoption.

Key Words: Virtual Tour, Traditional Places, Community Engagement, Crowdsourcing in Cultural Heritage, Gamification

INTRODUCTION

As climate change, natural disasters, modern development and human conflict proliferate and inflict significant impacts on the cultural landscapes of 21st-century society, traditional places are being damaged and lost in rapidly changing societies and environments (Bhatia & Shukla, 2024; Boshier *et al*, 2020; Sepe, 2023; Brosché *et al*, 2017). Risks faced by traditional places and heritage sites come from all varieties

of anthropogenic and natural sources. Current scholarship and action-based research have been elicited by researchers and policy makers to support indigenous capacity building in the heritage management field through the development of tools, practices, knowledge co-production methods and policies that can operationalize these principles to build and support an indigenous heritage data workforce and government efforts (Carroll *et al.*, 2020; Gupta *et al.*, 2023).

Dawson *et al.* noted that while indigenous youth are already engaged with emerging digital technologies through videogames, we as researchers still “need to better understand how indigenous users perceive the digital replicas we create, and under what conditions meanings are transferred, either in whole or in part, from the real object to its digital ‘replicant’” (2011: p. 399).

Vogel, Moulder & Huggins and the International Association for Public Participation define the five primary levels of public impact as inform, consult, involve, collaborate, and empower (2014). The influential Sámi cultural leader Marit Teigmo Eira “elaborated on the importance of [indigenous] perspectives” for the selection of cultural assets and their respective presentation mediums to reflect “their importance for the culture and values such as intuitivism, richness of ideas, flexibility, simplicity, and ingenuity (Magnani *et al.*, 2023: p. 94; Eira, 1988). Like Sami scholars that rapidly adopted digitalization of artifacts “to restore to life and bring to consciousness cultural heritage housed on distant shelves”, Carcross / Tagish First Nation (C/TFN) management were quick to support the digitalization of cultural sites, landscapes and features in their traditional territory for dissemination to community members both local and distant (Magnani *et al.*, 2023: p. 95).

Indigenous agency in the active preservation and amplification of intangible cultural heritage is decreed and supported by local, regional, national and international agreements (Marrie, 2008). As approximately 85% of Canadian organized contemporary archaeological activity is based “within the regulatory and interventionist environment of State land use planning” but indigenous representation in the professional heritage practice in Canada only ranges from 3-5.3%, it is imperative to identify and proliferate heritage management applications that indigenous communities find engaging and reflective of preferred land management principles (Dent, 2019: p. 26; La Salle and Hutchings, 2012; Ferris, 2007; Ontario, 2016, Jalbert,

2019 and Hodgetts *et al* 2020; as cited in Rowinski 2023). When considering planning and compliance-based heritage activities, Noe found the inclusion of immersive technologies in technical documentation may contribute to the ongoing conversation of ethical design and collaborative decision-making in the development of management alternatives and application of appropriate actions (2021). C/TFN's Traditional Territory is in what is presently known as the Southern Lakes region of Southern Yukon Territory and Northern British Columbia in Western Canada. The C/TFN constitution includes mandates to “protect the environment, health, education and aboriginal rights of [their] Citizens; to continue to preserve and protect [their] culture, traditions and languages; to protect and develop [their] natural resources and strengthen [their] economy and the Carcross/Tagish First Nation government for [their] future generations” (C/TFN, 2023a).

Existing approaches in heritage engagement and management in Canada are dominated by the use of 2D assets including documents, photographs and maps. As noted by Bianchini *et al.*, photos of archaeological data may be affected by subjective interpretation, thus 360-degree photos may reduce subjectivity by providing an immersive frame of reference (2015). Evens, Empsen and Hustinx concluded that 360-degree videos produce positive effects on attitude, immersion and presence, empathy, perceptions of technology and self-efficacy (2022). D’Alba found that participants who experienced a virtual museum prior to attending the museum in person had a positive experience when visiting the physical space due to their knowledge of what they were going to find (2013).

Digital approaches to the safeguarding and interpretation of traditional places and cultural landscapes have expanded in the last decades as technological innovation has decreased the cost and complexity of sensors and computers. CyArk, Google Arts and Culture, Rekrei, Iconem, Factum Foundation, and 3DHOP APIs and online viewer implementations, all leading cultural heritage digital preservation organizations, create 3D models, viewers and 3D Virtual Tours of heritage sites across the world (Statham, 2019; Marek, 2022). General Geographic Information System (GIS) software such as ESRI ArcGIS, QGIS, and Arches is used to keep track of the locations of heritage sites, landscape features, maps, metadata and perform spatial analysis. 360-degree panorama images and videos have been used to provide users

with virtual visits to locations for remote education and interpretation or in-person tourism (Dawson *et al*, 2018; Wu and Lai, 2022).

Contributing to this discourse, this paper is occupied with a significant case of threat of losing an example of intangible Cultural Heritage. In the Canadian north, there is evidence that youth are not participating to the same degree as their forefathers in the traditional modes of skill transmission, including “on-the-land education [and] hands-on, practical engagement with the environment”, due to being raised “exclusively in the context of fixed settlements and Eurocentric education” (Pearce *et al.*, 2011: p. 271).

Recently, C/TFN has begun compiling an online geospatial database of their TEK and Traditional Places to support mapping and data organizational processes as well as consultation requests from the government and industry (Kwusen Research and Media, 2023). C/TFN has framed entries with the *Traditional Unit* (TU) nomenclature, under which they are separated into seven value sections, echoing European initiatives like the Faro Convention (Council of Europe, 2005). Each independent entry is then broken down into sub-types that fall within one of the seven value sections. C/TFN has selected each TU value to be included specifically because they believe it is important to safeguard these values and provide a plethora of tools to meet that end. C/TFN TUs are at risk from a plethora of direct and indirect impacts caused by human activity in their locales including recreation, housing infrastructure development, and power production, storage, and delivery infrastructure development (C/TFN, 2023c).

State of the Art

Restriction of data management and dissemination of documents and static representations of local knowledge, e.g. photographs, limits the ability of data users to grasp many aspects of TUs. The term *users* in this context C/TFN citizens and land managers, planners, heritage specialists, archaeologists, emergency responders, and others who need data to preserve, protect, and disseminate information about TUs. Typically, place names and TUs are presented in communicative media such as maps, photos, documents and spreadsheets. While all forms of cultural heritage data management and dissemination have their place, each previously listed mechanism

alone and even combined may be problematic for defining the holistic lifeways that accompany any value attributed to TUs by many indigenous groups.

Issues in data capture activities include a lack of time, financial resources, trained specialists, and regulatory and remoteness impediments to TUs. Issues in information dissemination come from the overtly technical design and verbiage of regulatory documentation, the underutilization of intuitive heritage site visualization software, and a misunderstanding of development opportunities associated with cultural heritage. Issues with heritage data management come from complex and fluid hardware and software needs, unrecorded legacy management decisions, uninformed communication guidelines, and the lack of detailed and strict template adherence regulations for heritage records. As noted by Gupta *et al.*, “training and building capacity in digital methods and data practice is central in supporting innovation and community governance of digital heritage” (2023: p. 85).

Napolitano *et al.* found that a VT and informational modeling integration was effective remote assessments of cultural heritage structures and the initial documentation and communication of associated problems (2018). Through their evaluation of a Virtual Tour at the Hailongtun World Heritage Site in Guizhou Province, China, Ren and Chen found that remote visitors felt Virtual Tours were more effective at “highlighting outstanding universal values of world cultural heritage” than traditional methods, and that VTs “generally conform to the seven interpretation and presentation principles” of the 2008 Charter for the Interpretation and Presentation of Cultural Heritage Sites (2020: p. 1209; I.C.O.M.O.S., 2008). Harun and Mahadzir have shown that VTs can be produced as a digital database for management of traditional buildings and as a simple, low-cost provision of remote access to unique heritage values for digital visitors (2021).

Materials and Methods

The presented research builds on this finding through the integration of a sample of C/TFN’s geospatial TU database (Community Knowledge Keeper - CKK) within two prototype Virtual Tours (VTs). This effort aimed to provide two options (Virtual Tours and 3D representations of sites) to immerse C/TFN citizens and staff in digital documentations of their past cultural landscapes and current lifeways. By presenting TUs as immersive digital environments, multifaceted information held by community

members and groups can be intuitively shared and disseminated through increased feelings of presence. VTs which utilize 360-degree photos are selected here as an ideal conduit for widespread adoption of immersive media in the heritage space due to the 360-degree camera's relative low cost, prolific tour compilation and dissemination software options, and diverse presentation mediums including the ubiquitous mobile phone, tablets, laptops, monitors, VR headsets, projectors, etc.

This research responds to the “pressing need in our contemporary societies [to strengthen] individual and collective identity [and include and integrate] information stored in individuals’ memories... as well as complex and conceptual knowledge” with heritage education and preservation priorities (Artopoulos *et al.*, 2018: p.108). Prior research has identified the need to “actively involve community members within the entire development process” for more ethical and less extractive software development methodologies in consideration of the community of the cultural heritage under investigation (LaPensée, 2020 and E-Line Media, 2014, as cited in Noe, 2021; Noe, 2021). This research was conducted with three objectives:

1. to provide a roadmap for the adoption of accessible, engaging and user-friendly emerging technologies by heritage practitioners and concerned entities in preservation of sensitive sites that are threatened by human activity and climate pressures, and in particular for the valorization of sites that are not protected;
2. to describe the benefits and disadvantages of the afore mentioned tools in site visualization and communication with the purpose to increase engagement of indigenous youth and communities with traditional places in their traditional territory;
3. to explore the benefit of accessing digital assets of survey documentations enriched with existing written, recorded, drawn and archived information through immersive interfaces on the expansion of a knowledge classification system.

The paper presents how this research aims to build on this foundation to identify opportunities for the C/TFN Land Management Board (LMB) to incorporate three types of emerging technologies (360-degree Virtual Tours, 180-degree 3D videos, and 3D reality capture models and heritage asset representations) with their community engagement/heritage management activities and data sovereignty goals. 360-degree

Virtual Tours were chosen as the primary knowledge access interface because they have been proven to positively affect perceptions of usefulness and satisfaction, may reduce subjectivity in digital representations of TUs, and effectively integrate the natural and virtual worlds (Sepasgozar, 2022; Bianchini *et al*, 2015; Dawson *et al* 2011).

[A Prototype Application of Virtual Tours in Cultural Heritage Knowledge Elicitation](#)

The methodology for this work is inspired by fundamental elements of the Indigenous Evaluation Framework (IEF) epistemology described by LaFrance, Nichols and Kirkhart (2018; 2012). Research productions were designed to share the continuously evolving stories of traditional places through data collection and immersive organization, presentation, conversation, and enrichment.

For the development of this research, suitable locations within their traditional territory were provided by the C/TFN Executive Council and LMB for the creation of VTs: a hunting blind site on Chílíh DzéÉe'/Tsálgi Shaayi, and the area around Désdélé Méne', L'ál Héeni/Gáąsé Tóo'e and the Watson River. The Community Knowledge Keeper (CKK; C/TFN's internal GIS database), GeoYukon (the territorial government's public-access geospatial database) and Hare and Greer's *Désdélé Méne' The Archaeology of Annie Lake* were reviewed for heritage information related to the two locations (2023b; 2023; 1994). TU descriptions in the CKK were the primary sources of heritage site classifier identification and archaeological data. Prototype Virtual Tours were then created for a presentation to the C/TFN LMB, after which they were provided with a survey to collect feedback.

Research indicated the Chílíh DzéÉe'/Tsálgi Shaayi Hunting Blind site (Figure 1) had one related entry in the CKK. It was noted that the site was revisited and recorded again in 2018; however, the updated information was not available in the CKK at the time of research.

The research involved fieldwork, diagnosis and site documentation with the support of two C/TFN Natural Resource Technicians in two locations on two days in November 2023. Fieldwork relied on two mobile phones to create 3D models and utilized a Garmin GPS to geolocate captured imagery.

Figure 1: Map of research area by the author. Place names are in Tagish/Tlingit/English languages as available. Place names were sourced from Hare and Greer (1994) and Hayman et al. (2017), originally from Sidney (1980).

Figure 2: The author and C/TFN Natural Resource Technician recording Northern Blinds.

The C/TFN Technicians video-recorded the blinds with 360-degree and 180-degree 3D cameras. 3D models of eight hunting blinds were created using LiDAR and

Photogrammetry mobile solutions. Further to site documentation, imagery from vantage points were recorded for future users to understand how the site's specific location relates to other features on the landscape. A herd of caribou were encountered during the fieldwork - as the blinds are for Caribou hunting, the opportunity to capture footage of the caribou was a welcome opportunity to integrate additional components of C/TFN lifeways in the prototype Virtual Tours.

Research for the second VT, *Désdélé Méne'* (Figure 1), consisted of reviewing the CKK and Hare and Greer's *Désdélé Méne' The Archaeology of Annie Lake*, provided by C/TFN (1994). When planning perspective-capture locations, viewsheds along the entirety the lake area were prioritized; high points near Annie Lake Road were identified to ensure views of the northern and southern portions of the lake were identified from public access points.

At the northern extent of *Désdélé Méne'*, the crew travelled towards the location of the significant excavations from 1982-1992 and reached a high terrace overlooking the excavation site as well as *Désdélé Méne'*, surrounding mountain peaks, trails, and historical human-use indicators, of which both 360-degree and 3D video imagery was collected.

Figure 3: Mining claims (tree in foreground and another, center background) above *Désdélé Méne'*.

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Fieldwork was also conducted near hydrological monitoring sites. As we know from Wilson, Hayman *et al.*, and C/TFN's Natural Resource Technicians, good water

quality is an integral component of C/TFN lifeways (2019; 2017; NRT, 2023). An on-the-fly decision was made to also include two water-sampling locations and one permafrost-monitoring station in the VT. Two water sampling sites at the southern extent of the research area were visited: a bridge over L'ál Héeni/Gáásé Tóo'e (Wheaton River) and a large pullout adjacent to the Watson River that had a rock ring and is a well-used camping site used by C/TFN citizens and other visitors throughout the year (NRT, 2023).

Figure 4: C/TFN Natural Resource Technicians recording a 3D video at the L'ál Héeni/Gáásé Tóo'e bridge water sampling site.

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The Pano2VR VT Software was utilized for the creation of the prototype tours due to its ease of use, affordable academic license, clean presentation, extensive capabilities and library of documentation and tutorials available online. The 360-degree imagery was captured in video format rather than as photographs to collect the maximum number of perspectives given the time and weather restraints in the field.

Figure 54: North Blinds concentration point of interest, with additional blind hotspots in center and Western Overlook hotspot on right. C/TFN Natural Resource Technicians in center.

A video segment of Caribou in the vicinity of the blinds was embedded in the “Carcross Overlook” point of interest to ensure continuity of perspective between the point of interest and the video.

Figure 6: Caribou video footage integration at "Carcross Overlook" point of interest.

Sixteen hotspots were incorporated in the Chłłh DzéÉe’/Tsálgi Shaayi Hunting Blinds VT. As Quartly identified a clear preference for launching VTs from hotspots

within a map-based interface, each panorama was assigned locational data and Pano2VR's integrated mapmaker was utilized to provide this option (2015).

Figure 7: 3D models from Chilh Dzele'/Tsalgi Shaayi fieldwork stored in Sketchfab Pro account for security (password protected) and dissemination.

Due to the diversity of captured TUs, landscapes and availability of background information, the compilation of the Désdélé Méne' Prototype VT required extensive consideration. The point located on Annie Lake Road on the north end of Désdélé Méne' was chosen as the starting point because of its public accessibility and viewshed.

Figure 8: Opening perspective from Désdélé Méne' Prototype Virtual Tour

The Désdélé Méne' North Overlook hotspot incorporates two unique features which provide context of C/TFN lifeways in the vicinity, in addition to other hotspots in the VT. The first consists of an excerpt of Hare and Greer's archaeological data (1994). The second incorporates CKK data about TUs that are located on a Mountain Peak visible to the West.

Figure 9: Excerpts from Hare and Greer incorporated in hotspot at excavation location (1994).

The Annie Lake South Overlook hotspot was designed to provide viewers with context regarding public availability of C/TFN data; a heritage site which was highlighted during C/TFN's land claim negotiations with the Yukon Territorial Government is located. This site's georeferenced boundary is visible on the public facing GeoYukon website as shown in the hotspot in Figure 21 (Government of Yukon, 2023).

Figure 10: Popup from hotspot indicating presence of publicly available heritage data on GeoYukon website (Government of Yukon, 2023).

As the Désdélé Méne' Virtual Tour encompassed a large area, it was not possible to link all the points of interest together visually through hotspots. To visit each point (or compilation of points that are visually linked) the user has two options: one is the tour point selection bar, the other is the tour map. For Désdélé Méne' a separate map created with Google Earth Pro was provided, rather than utilizing Pano2VR's integrated map maker, to provide an alternative geospatial perspective and investigate C/TFN's preferred map style. Hotspots on the map are clickable and jump the user to that location.

Figure 11: Désdélé Méne' point of interest map interface. Note: "Watson River Sampling Site" was left off the map due to its location ~6km north of the Permafrost Monitoring Station, inclusion of which made it hard to read the other point of interest identifiers.

The Cabin Foundation, Trail and CMT site was turned into a three-hotspot section intended to present the close spatial relationship between a modern road, a well-defined and currently well-used trail bed, a traditional subsistence feature, and a historic habitation feature from multiple perspectives. South of the Annie Lake Road is a Trapline TU. A text box was incorporated in the second location to provide the user with the notes from the original recorder of the TU (C/TFN, 2023b). These two points of interest were chosen to present the relationship between previously identified TUs, their contemporary status and setting, and adjacent features that may be related to the original classification of the TU.

Figure 152: Trail, Cabin foundation (background, right), and CMT (foreground, right) in Désdélé Méne' area.

The Watson River Water Sampling Site is to the north of Désdélé Méne', the L'ál Héeni/Gáąsé Tóo'e (Wheaton River) Water Sampling Site 1, and the L'ál Héeni/Gáąsé Tóo'e Camp and Water Sampling Site 2 were chosen to highlight the exact location that water samples come from, their immediate vicinities and indications of the strong continued connection between people and the L'ál Héeni/Gáąsé Tóo'e in this area.

Figure 13: L'ál Héeni/Gáqsé Tóó'e River campsite with 3D model hotspot at the stone fire ring and water sampling site hotspot adjacent to the river.

The Permafrost Monitoring Station POI is incorporated into the VT to inform the public and highlight another type of environmental factor being monitored by C/TFN.

Figure 14: Permafrost monitoring station; Natural Resource Technician recording a 3D video of a sensor mounted on the tree while the author processes a 3D model on his phone.

To maximize the benefits for the community and minimize barriers to adoption of the workflow, low-cost, high-mobility and ease-of-use were prioritized during the

equipment selection. Hardware utilized included Insta360 OneX2 and Evo cameras and iPhone 12 Pro and LG G8X ThinQ mobile phones. Software included Insta360 Studio 2023, Pano2VR, Insta360 mobile apps, Scaniverse and Polycam mobile apps, Garmin Basecamp, Google Earth Pro, and the Sketchfab website.

RESULTS

The Prototype Virtual Tours were presented in a closed session to C/TFN's LMB in November 2023. The discussion was laid out as 15-minute presentation of each Prototype Virtual Tour followed by 15 minutes of discussion and results; however, LMB questions were voiced organically and the associated conversation consumed the time intentionally reserved for discussion. The flexibility necessary for an open-concept presentation method is congruent with an indigenous paradigm based on storytelling traditions and “is relational as conversation is a natural way to gather knowledge between individuals” and “understanding the lived experience of other people and the meaning they make of that experience” (White Eyes, 2023: p.40-41; Seidman, 2019: p. 9, as cited in White Eyes, 2023; Kovach, 2010). During the discussion, members and guests of the C/TFN LMB voiced a sample of their opinions and intentions for future use of Virtual Tours. There were four primary findings identified during the discussion:

1. A request for opportunities to immerse citizens in digital environments especially augmented with C/TFN traditional languages, Tagish and Tlingit.
2. A request to remove the field crew and field vehicles from the 360s.
3. A request for total integration of the CKK and the Virtual Tour interfaces.
4. Significantly, there was a communal agreement that C/TFN will be utilizing this emerging technology tool in the future, and that there was no foreseen limit for what could be portrayed through these types of digital interfaces that C/TFN would find valuable. A case study consisting of presenting hazardous/contaminated sites to the community with a Virtual Tour was suggested, to limit exposure to more citizens than necessary.

Following up on this, the author had informal conversations with community representatives about heritage information visualizations, engaging digital interfaces, and the use of immersive virtual experiences for community engagement with traditional places.

Figure 15: The field crew discussing the different ways to capture and present perspectives of traditional sites.

The discussion focused on barriers to access more remote traditional places in C/TFN's territory and the perceived lack of interest among the youth to learn more about the associated areas. The commonality of video game use among youth in the community came up, and the possibility of gamifying these prototype Virtual Tours was discussed as a concept for further exploration.

Figure 16: Proposed workflow co-developed through action-based research and user feedback. Key focus points include: a detailed collaborative planning phase to ensure understanding of potential needs and production impacts (Steps 1 & 2); incorporating youth-led interviews with knowledge holders to guide field investigations for intergenerational sharing and insure post-interview data compilation sessions with research time are conducts (Step 3); conduct pre-fieldwork language learning sessions, especially for resources likely to be encountered (Step 4); conduct practice sessions with community members on the use of digital recording equipment prior fieldwork (Step 5); prioritize interview and conversation-based methods of assessment and feedback with a variety of community member in a variety of settings to maximize knowledge elicitation (Step 6); iterate and assess virtual tours incrementally so evolution of the product can occur as additional places are visited and tours are created (Steps 7-9); test integrations with local GIS systems already utilized by the community to minimize the implementation of additional software complexities (Step 10); incorporate common community verbiage and skills in the instruction and training material for the creation and use of developed tools (Step 11); initiate a social media plan for community outreach (Step 12); assess community use of tools based on resources available in the community (Step 13); plan action review and final discussion with Indigenous government and share findings aligned with local cultural governance procedures (Step 14).

Indigenous management of priorities for Virtual Tour site selection and design has been identified as a factor that defines success or lack thereof. The first focus of this research was the presentation of visual information and landscapes in an

immersive digital environment. While the visual experience was prioritized during VT production, the inclusion of Tagish/Tlingit language text within the VT interface may have achieved the level of language integration C/TFN was interested in seeing. POIs within the tours could be augmented with superimposed place names and/or words relating to the TU features and components.

Integrations of the VTs with C/TFN's CKK database can be achieved through the incorporation of a hyperlink in that TU's metadata page. Hosting the VTs online comes with additional security complexities that must be considered to ensure C/TFN's sovereignty over their digital resources.

C/TFN's interest in exploring the application of this research in future endeavors adds credence to the value given to immersive visualizations of cultural heritage. In the future, the creation of a knowledge base of information representation will enable cross-compatibility, interoperability with libraries, re-use and open access. This work focused on providing the C/TFN community with digital representations of TUs in their traditional territory. C/TFN may choose to utilize this research to guide new forms of consultation deliverables from industries requesting to develop projects in their traditional territory, or to develop guidance procedures for trail crews working around sensitive resources, or target youth at different ages, for example.

The gamification of VTs to attract interest and action from C/TFN community youth was an inspiration for this research and, while unattainable with the time and resources available, is explorable as evidenced by the youth's interest in the concept. Gamification as a method for exploration of cultural heritage, educating the public, and reconnecting indigenous youth with TEK has been explored extensively throughout literature and continues to elicit further research (Karahan and Gül, 2021; Bonacini and Giaccone, 2022; Robles-Bykbaev *et al.*, 2018; Mwangonde *et al.*, 2021; Nijdam, 2023). Similarly, further research on the integration of 3D models and video with the VTs is necessary.

DISCUSSION

This paper presented an easily accessible and replicable workflow to incorporate emerging immersive technological tools as options for indigenous communities to utilize throughout efforts to safeguard their threatened immaterial cultural heritage and

historical cultural landscapes. The C/TFN LMB's remarks regarding clarification about the expansion of traditional place names presence in the Virtual Tours is indicative of the wider indigenous call for aboriginal management of "the preservation, revitalization and strengthening of aboriginal languages and culture" (Truth and Reconciliation Commission, 2015: p. 2). The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance were conceived to complement the FAIR principles support the creation of value "from indigenous data in ways that are grounded in Indigenous worldviews and realize opportunities within the knowledge economy" (GIDA, 2023: p. 1).

Ontological representation and semantic modeling of indigenous knowledge, as well as the relevant vocabularies used in databases of cultural sites inventories for scholarly support and common regulated record-keeping (though these are initiatives which are designed and adopted by the colonial state) utilize categorizations that often diminish and/or misrepresent the resilience of Indigenous communities and lifeways (Platt, 2011, Schneider & Hayes, 2020). Peter Nelson and Schneider & Hayes argue that archaeological and historical archives expose the flattening of Indigenous cultural sites when viewed from the perspective of an archaeologist that is an Indigenous member of the living community under study (Schneider & Hayes, 2020). Ultimately, this paper lays groundwork which, in addition to youth/community engagement, can contribute to more transparent and inclusive Indigenous knowledge representation, if connected with existing scholarly efforts of capturing and representing the many Indigenous ways of living in nature. This effort is expected in the future to contribute to defining in a more accurate way terms (in vocabularies) that better represent each culture's collective, yet heterogeneous, worldviews and values (Aikenhead and Ogawa 2007). This effort in enabling dispersed community members to collectively decide on how to document and represent their knowledge, is based on the premise of "a special classification scheme [which] may be more appropriate for a collection of materials for or about a specific group of people" (Green, 2015: p. 212).

Co-design of digital learning environments has been called for to support historically marginalized communities to develop and adopt culturally appropriate technologies, integrate protocol practices, and embed Indigenous perspectives in digital learning environments (Bayeck & Asino, 2024; Neden, 2023; Koole, Traxler & Footring, 2022). Research regarding the valorization of immersive media should continue to identify if immersive data management systems are able to realize

indigenous worldviews more effectively (GIDA, 2023). The paper argues that 360-degree Virtual Tours and 3D models should continue to be co-created and assessed within indigenous knowledge management contexts to ensure culturally sensitive methodologies are established and “can assist indigenous communities in fulfilling their own visions of heritage preservation” (DeHass & Taitt, 2018: p. 120). As envisioned by Nasrolahi *et al*, innovative methods of community collaboration with decision-makers through the provision of potential project data and associated landscape change visualizations may “help people to understand the reasons behind the implementation of planned activities” (2022: p. 2), and thus encourage community interest and support for citizen youth to enter heritage and environment-based professions (Antoniou *et al*, 2022).

This paper aims to inform the adoption of immersive heritage management systems to promote indigenous perspectives and priorities in accessible mediums which provides an intuitive understanding of tangible and intangible cultural heritage and the risks they face. While these measures can be adopted by corporate developers and Western governmental agencies charged with the management of heritage resources in their care, the current state of the research presented is focused on C/TFN participant’s perspectives on the effectiveness of immersive digital documentation procedures and products to document and communicate Traditional Places and TU components. Community assessment has shown the proposed method to be a promising contribution towards the safeguarding of threatened, often overlooked tangible and intangible cultural heritage for younger generations to engage with.

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